

TASK SIMULATION USING HUMAN FIGURE MODELS

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Summary

Modern design evaluation technologies based on human figure simulations are helping us to make fuller and more accurate assessments of human/machine and workplace interfaces. As computer graphics and related digital technologies advance, we will be able to illustrate, predict, evaluate, and document a wider array of human performance issues involving system useability concurrently with design development. The Design Evaluation for Personnel, Training, and Human Factors (DEPTH) program is developing and integrating many of these technologies for engineering applications. This paper provides an overview of current and planned DEPTH technology developments.

Introduction

There are several advantages in bringing human factors evaluation directly into the CAD engineering environment. First, accurately scaled human figures can be shown interacting with accurate models of the equipment or work environment being designed. This creates a type of virtual prototyping capability to augment or replace hard prototypes for many types of traditional human factors analysis. Second, the results of CAD-based human modeling are easier to understand and to communicate because they rely on visualization. Third, CAD-based simulations of human performance can be replayed quickly and inexpensively to illustrate the effects of an altered design.

Most CAD-based human modeling technologies have been developed with the aim of evaluating physical accommodation of humans in the work environment. That is, the stress has been on evaluating body size/fit,

reach, posture, comfort, and strength through graphical simulation that places a human-like figure in digital representations of the equipment and/or environment on the CAD screen.

The DEPTH program is enhancing and extending this technology in several ways. First, we are developing and using *animated* human models to assess human movement and interaction with the CAD environment. Animation allows more complete evaluation of human performance issues across entire task sequences. It also adds visual realism to task simulations. Second, we are looking at ways to aggregate human performance data and to match specific design rules with the results of human/product simulations. This will allow us to perform "prescriptive" simulations that instantiate what we know about human performance abilities directly in human figure simulations. Third, we will connect human performance simulation within the CAD environment with Logistics Support Analysis (LSA) processes that define system support resources. This objective is in consonance with concurrent engineering and CALS objectives for design data automation and management.

Equipment maintenance task analysis information is a key element of system support documentation. This is inherently human-centered. Many data elements from the task analysis results can be accurately and inexpensively verified and documented if CAD engineering technology can be linked with LSA processes. Maintenance technical manuals and other product support documents will be easier to produce and update with fuller use of human modeling technology. A natural corollary use of human modeling technology is in creating digital technical training media. We expect DEPTH

technology to make important contributions in all these applications.

In summary, DEPTH human model simulations will be used first to influence a product's design for usability, and then to document the product support requirements for human-related logistics resources. The human modeling workstation currently under development is depicted in Figure 1.

Human Modeling Uses

A large number of human models have been developed since the late 1970's. While many early models used only human hands or arms to check clearances for tool manipulation, most current models create whole-body representations using a basic "link" system resembling a human skeleton to enable posturing of the model within the CAD work environment.

Early efforts to integrate human modeling with CAD resulted in building the models with the same graphics capabilities of the design software itself (e.g., IBM CATIA, CADAM, Computervision). While this facilitated integration of the human models with product models, performance limitations of the CAD systems with respect to model rotation, zoom, animation, and repositioning limited the capability to simulate dynamic interaction of the human model with the product model. Recent developments in the human modeling field include the adoption of high-speed graphics workstations as simulation platforms, use of CAD translators to import product geometry and related design information into the workstation, and dramatically better ability to animate and control human models interactively. DEPTH is building on these new foundations for human performance simulation.

Human modeling for maintainability will continue to stress physical criteria of task analysis, but new technology advances are opening up a wider array of applications. But the "higher" human factors involving personnel selection, job design, and training will also come within reach of human modeling. These are stressed in DEPTH.

Figure 1. The DEPTH human factors analysis workstation uses a modular software architecture that integrates graphic human models, human performance data bases and standards, simulation utilities, and CAD and Logistics Support Analysis Record (LSAR) software interfaces.

Technical Developments

The DEPTH program is nearing the end of Phase II of a five year, five-phase technology development effort that began in 1992.

Progress: An Integrated Baseline

In Phase I, we adopted the *Jack* model developed by the University of Pennsylvania as the core human modeling baseline for development of DEPTH. At the same time, we imported into the DEPTH workstation several unique features of the Air Force's Crew Chief model. This included the extensive data base on human strength amassed through the ergonomic research program of the Armstrong Laboratory's Crew Systems Directorate. We also translated the Crew Chief human figure models into the DEPTH environment so that they could be manipulated and animated using *Jack's* inverse kinematics algorithms. By merging elements of these two human modeling systems, we have created the basis for a more unified human modeling technology.

Forty seven human-modeling and robotics software packages were identified and evaluated before we chose to encapsulate

the University of Pennsylvania's *Jack* system for the central place in DEPTH software architecture (Figure 2). The DEPTH user interface provides seamless execution of *Jack* functionality and other analysis tools, such as the Human Operator Simulator (HOS) and Crew Chief strength data, through a common set of menus. The ability to incorporate existing models and data bases and to communicate among them with software sockets are key features of the DEPTH modular software architecture. These permit integration of software capabilities for future growth of the system without requiring source code for each new capability we add.

Progress: New Technologies for Human Figure Modeling

The DEPTH program is spurring leading edge research and new software tools for human modeling in conjunction with the Center for Human Modeling and Simulation at the University of Pennsylvania. The products of this work are found in *Jack* (not an acronym), an interactive graphics system for displaying and manipulating jointed, 3-D geometric figures. The *Jack* system (current release 5.8) includes a very wide array of software tools for maintenance task analysis using animated human figures. A few of these are discussed below.

Jack has a fully linked body model with 35-joints, including a 17-segment spine. The body dimensions are easily resized through an interactive spreadsheet utility to reflect body segment percentiles for any desired population or for specific persons. Joint centers and motion degrees of freedom are defined so that the human figure, when animated, moves with biomechanical realism.

Jack's inverse kinematics engine for human motion visualization relies on simultaneous constraint processing for each body joint. This permits real-time end-effector dragging through joint chains, allowing the user to see how the figure responds to reach or movement tasks. It also allows easier scripting of animation sequences (e.g., through HOS V) by allowing the user to specify high level movement goals (i.e., place the wrench on

the bolt) while *Jack* automatically processes the constraints of body positioning at a lower level.

For strength assessment, *Jack* can compute the strength requirements for human figures given postures. Interactive strength data displays list all torque loads along any selected chain of body segments. This allows motion simulation to be or constrained by known limits of human strength in different postures and joint loading conditions. In DEPTH, both dynamic and static strength analyses are combined through *Jack* and Crew Chief data integration. With the former, it is possible to simulate motions that account for human strength across an entire motion sequence. With the latter, maximum force in given body postures is displayed.

In addition to standard CAD imaging and translation tools, *Jack* also allows external control through operating system "sockets." We are using these to build communications between *Jack* and HOS V and other data bases. It is this connectivity and extensibility that will allow human modeling to become a player in networked computing environments needed for concurrent engineering.

Progress: Task Simulation Using Human Operator Simulator (HOS)

DEPTH includes a powerful tool for aiding task composition for animation and analysis. More accurate and detailed simulation of complex maintenance tasks are needed for more complete estimation of human performance requirements. This includes portrayal of behavior of the human model according to a logical plan of action that can be scripted by the analyst. One way this can be done in the DEPTH workstation is by using the Human Operator Simulator (HOS Version V) to create task networks that describe the work in terms of logical sequences of subtasks. A library of micro models is used to obtain estimates of task times for task primitives derived from ergonomic literature and predetermined task time data bases such as MTM. With this task network modeling tool we are able to show human figures acting out task sequences in

realistically timed motions. This HOS/Jack link is one of the key technical achievements for the DEPTH program so far. We have joined an advanced workload simulation tool (HOS Version V and Micro Saint) with Jack to provide near real time visualization of maintenance task sequences.

Support for task time prediction is provided by this integration through use of micro models within the HOS V system. Micro models are equations or algorithms that compute subtask times and accuracies. They are derived from empirical literature or from predetermined time systems.

Progress: Task Taxonomy Methods

To associate human abilities and skill requirements with maintenance and support tasks, two types of data be critical to our approach. The first type is human ability data and the second type is task data. These must be developed into a sufficiently detailed breakdown to permit identification or description of specific human attributes (e.g., dynamic strength, visual discrimination, fine-motor manipulation) or skills (e.g., using a torque wrench, reading technical orders) that are required for performance of task segments, or primitives, that are impacted by specific design characteristics and constraints (LRU location, type of fasteners or connectors, LRU weight, etc.) of the equipment under analysis. A major challenge Phase II has been to synthesize a taxonomic structure that will encompass all prospective maintenance and support personnel and evolving equipment designs, yet be sufficiently detailed to match specific human abilities with design-specific task characteristics.

Prospects: Advanced Human Factors Analysis

In Phase III, beginning in the Spring of 1994, our objective is to develop an advanced human factors analysis capability through the implementation of "prescriptive" level design evaluation technology. This will provide the DEPTH user with information sources,

interface tools, and display formats for integration and analysis of physical, perceptual and psychomotor limitations and safety considerations into the design process.

We will conduct a government and industry survey to identify the needs of potential DEPTH users and preferred data presentation formats for communicating analysis results to design and logistics engineers. We will seek ways to use human performance data from various sources to inform human modeling and task analysis within the DEPTH workstation.

Figure 2. The University of Pennsylvania's Jack Version 5.8 is the core of the human modeling system within DEPTH.

The identification of requirements and approaches for enhancement of DEPTH capabilities to meet the needs of potential users will be input to a technology survey update to assess information, analysis and synthesis technologies applicable to DEPTH enhancement. Additionally, the "digitization" of data sources, such as MIL-STD-1472, Air Force Lessons Learned, military handbooks and design guides, occupational safety and hazardous materials information, will be assessed for on-screen presentation to the designer. Initially, related standards may be provided in a "help" window with a search capability on descriptive nouns for the type of

equipment being designed. Further DEPTH development may enable an automatic search of the data bases corresponding to the design name or the names of significant components within the design, such as "fuel pump" or "hydraulic actuator."

In addition to providing a DEPTH user access to and meaningful display of relevant data impacting human performance issues, a Phase III capability to be developed is a rule-checking and prescriptive design capability for identification of and recommending correction to design problems.

Prospects: New Capabilities

The Phase IV objective for DEPTH is to develop enhancements for graphical human-modeling simulation and analysis. This includes simulation of fine-motor skills, hand movement, visibility analysis, simulation of multi-person cooperative maintenance tasks, anthropometric representation of different population groups, and estimation of the effects of environmental stressors on physical workload and performance. Phase IV will also involve technology demonstrations with virtual reality devices for controlling human models.

Prospects: LSA, Training, and Human Resources Applications

The Phase V objective is to develop enhancements for data integration to provide user-friendly interfaces for analysis, documentation, and database update of logistics, training, and personnel selection issues involving job design.

By Phase V, two years from now, the DEPTH databases will encompass a comprehensive amount of visual and non-visual data, ranging from human anthropometry and performance capabilities to weapon system models and hardware attributes. We will perform a technology review to determine the specific data requirements for personnel skills analysis, effective presentation of human modeling graphics for technician training, and

organization of the required data elements for input to the logistics support analysis record (LSAR).

We will use the data requirements for the MIL-STD-1388-2B LSAR model to identify those data elements contained in DEPTH databases and those generated during maintenance task simulation that can be assembled into a data file for export to the LSAR. Task elements such as estimated times will be developed from a combination of measuring elapsed time during simulation and calculating times based on time associated with task primitives such as connector removal or curing and drying times of sealants and paint.

We will then identify and evaluate relevant technologies for "capturing" simulation data for input to the LSAR. This may include "reverse engineering" of the task decomposition work done during the task automation studies during Phase II to identify the appropriate higher level verbs (remove/replace) and nouns (parts, assemblies/tools) associated with the task descriptors in the LSAR and training documentation.

The LSAR information can also be organized into collections of tasks associated with an individual worker and his or her respective job specialty for allocation to higher level jobs. Optimization of allocation of jobs to individual workers or job specialties may then be performed through passing task sequence and time information to a discrete event simulation program. We are working with colleagues at Armstrong Lab to join DEPTH task simulation with another modeling system called MPT/DSS for this purpose. We are also collaborating with Army research colleagues to create task visualization tools to support Hardman III models. The HOS/*Jack* integration effort is one example of this collaboration.

As maintenance procedures are developed and job content is allocated, simulation using VR technology such as cyber gloves may be used for verification of job design and training.

As Figure 3 below shows, DEPTH is a way of specifying, analyzing, and documenting maintenance work using computer-generated video simulation and evaluation of maintenance tasks. It supports both design influence and resource planning roles for human aspects of system support through its integration with CAD, the origin of design engineering information, and with LSAR, the destination of human-centered support information.

Prospects: Technology Transition

Our technology development strategy includes parallel work with users to define requirements and technology demonstrations. It also seeks out partnerships with other government labs and industry groups with common interests in advancing this technology and spurring its use in both military and civilian application.

With our primary customer, Oklahoma City Air Logistics Center, we have used DEPTH to evaluate human factors aspects of B-1B avionics maintenance work in a technology demonstration project. At the same time, we have established working relationships with General Electric Military Engines, Hughes Training Systems, Lockheed Aerospace, and other users of human modeling technology in the defense industry for DEPTH beta testing and demonstration projects.

We have joined an SAE group on human modeling technology that is trying to develop standards for this field. With the Army Research Laboratory we are coordinating the development of joint-use human modeling tools. We are collaborating with the University of Iowa's Center for Computer-Aided Design on maintainability analysis tools for use in concurrent engineering. We are partnered with Iowa in a defense conversion program proposal, yet unfunded, to bring DEPTH the human modeling workstation into a research consortium supporting the heavy vehicle and construction equipment industry in the upper Midwest. Iowa is already using DEPTH in work funded by ARPA for maintainability analysis.

Dual-use applications of DEPTH technology are also being explored with Northwest Airlines and General Motors.

Finally, with funding from the Defense Simulation Modeling Office (DMSO), we are adapting DEPTH technology to simulate ground maintenance operations in a virtual battlefield environment through Distributed Interactive Simulation (DIS). This work is funded under a DMSO award to the Air Force, Army, and Marine Corps for joint-Service development. With DIS connectivity for DEPTH, it will become possible to produce realistic and economical evaluations of system support concepts through virtual prototyping of system operations over computer networks.

Figure 3. Specifying, Analyzing, and Documenting Maintenance Work in DEPTH.

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